

Reactions of *cis*-Dichlorobis(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) Chloride in Aqueous solution in presence of 1,10-Phenanthroline, 2,2'-Dipyridyl and Glycine

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The replacement of chloride ligands from *cis*-dichlorobis(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) ion in absence of acids in aqueous solution proceeds at a rate which is not affected by a bidentate ligand such as 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-dipyridyl or glycine. Under the experimental conditions the second chloride ion is released very much faster than the first through the reaction of $\text{Cr(en)}_2(\text{OH})\text{Cl}^+$ which is the conjugate base of the primary aquation product, $\text{Cr(en)}_2(\text{OH}_2)\text{Cl}^{2+}$. The experimentally determined rate constant is the one corresponding to the release of the first chloride (since $k_2 \gg k_1$). At 25°: k_1 , $1.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$; ΔH_1^\ddagger , 16.5 kcal/mole; ΔS_1^\ddagger , -20.0 e.u. The ΔS_1^\ddagger value is close to the value for the entropy of solvation of chloride ion suggesting dissociation mechanism for the aquation. Spectral observations have shown that dinuclear diol complexes of chromium(III) are formed in the systems as a result of subsequent slower changes.

CONSIDERABLE amount of information is available on the kinetics of reactions of bisethylenediamine complexes of chromium(III)¹. *Cis*-dichlorobis(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) chloride is known to aquate in acid medium in two stages². An attempt was made to study the kinetics of the possible replacement of both the complex bound chloride ions in *cis*-dichlorobis(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) ion by bidentate ligands such as 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-dipyridyl and glycine, the results of which are reported here.

Experimental

Materials: Tris(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) chloride, $[\text{Cr(en)}_3]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was prepared following the method of Bailar and Work³ and its purity was checked by analysis [Found: Cr, 13.10; N, 21.0 per cent. Calcd. for $[\text{Cr(en)}_3]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cr, 12.95; N, 20.92 per cent].

Pure sample of *cis*-dichlorobis(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) chloride, $\text{cis-}[\text{Cr(en)}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, was prepared from tris(ethylenediamine)chromium(III) chloride by the method described in literature⁴. Its purity was checked by analysis [Found: Cr, 17.6; N, 19.0 per cent. Calcd. for $[\text{Cr(en)}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cr, 17.54; N, 18.88 per cent].

1,10-Phenanthroline, 2,2'-dipyridyl and glycine used were of reagent grade (G.R.,E. Merck).

Distilled water redistilled in an all-glass still with a little potassium permanganate and alkali was used for making all experimental solutions which were stored in Jena glass vessels.

Method: A Philips conductance bridge (Type PR 9500/90) was used for measuring the resistances (Conductance = 1/Resistance) of the solutions in a stoppered conductivity cell; absorbance measurements were made with a Hilger Uvispek Spectrophotometer (H.700) using stoppered quartz cells of suitable light paths.

Requisite quantity of the complex (to give a concentration of 0.0002M in the final solution) was dissolved quickly in conductivity water thermostated at the experimental temperature and the time was noted from this stage onward. The solution was immediately transferred to the conductivity cell placed in the thermostat and the resistance of the solution was measured immediately and thereafter at suitable time intervals. The process of dissolution of the complex and the measurement of the first resistance value was completed within three minutes. The conductance of the solution increased with time due to release of the bound chloride ions. The pseudo-first-order rate constant, k_{obs} , for each experiment was evaluated graphically by the method of Guggenheim⁵ by plotting $-\log(C_{t+\tau} - C_t)$ vs. time (t), where C_t is the conductance of the experimental solution at time (t) and τ is a suitable constant time interval. The rate plots thus obtained for different temperatures have been found to be good straight lines. For following the rate of reaction in presence of the bidentate ligands, 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-dipyridyl or glycine, an aqueous solution containing the requisite quantity of the ligand was thermostated at the experimental temperature, then a known quantity of the complex was dissolved in it quickly, the volume immediately made up with thermostated water and the resistance of the solution was measured at suitable time intervals and the rate constants were evaluated by the method of Guggenheim as mentioned above.

Under the experimental conditions both the complex bound chloride ions were found to be released simultaneously (or at least the release of the second chloride was much faster than that of the first). This was concluded from the fact that the rate constant as obtained by the method of Guggenheim was more or less identical to that obtained by the usual first-order plot [plot of $\log(C_\infty - C_0)/(C_\infty - C_t)$ vs. time (t), where C_0 , C_t and C_∞ are the conductance values of the experimental solution at zero time, time, t , and at infinite time

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respectively], using for C_{∞} three times the 'zero time' conductance value i.e., the value expected for the release of both the chloride ions. In fact, after a sufficiently long time interval, the conductance value of the aqueous solution both in presence and absence of 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-dipyridyl or glycine attained a limiting value (this remained unchanged for a few days) which was comparable to that of a solution of $[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ of the same molar concentration as that of the $\text{cis-}[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ present originally in the experimental solution. The 'zero time' conductance value used in estimating C_{∞} was obtained by plotting conductance C_t vs. time (t) and extrapolating to $t=0$.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first-order rate constant, k_{obs} , values obtained in presence and absence of the reagents and at different temperatures (20°, 25°, 30° and 35°) are listed in Table-1.

TABLE 1

Pseudo-first-order rate constant, k_{obs} , values under different conditions : $\text{cis-}[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, 0.0002M

Temp., °C	[Reagent], Molar	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^2$ (a) min ⁻¹	
20	0	0.93 (0.98)	
	0	1.56 (1.64)	
	phen, 0.002	1.52	
	phen, 0.003	1.54	
	phen, 0.004	1.55	
	phen, 0.005	1.57	
	dipy, 0.002	1.57	
	dipy, 0.003	1.54	
	dipy, 0.004	1.55	
	dipy, 0.005	1.56	
	glycine, 0.002	1.56	
	glycine, 0.005	1.55	
	30	0	2.51 (2.70)
		0	3.91 (3.53)

(a) The k_{obs} values have been evaluated graphically by the method of Guggenheim ; the values within parentheses have been evaluated graphically by the usual relation for first-order reaction using for C_{∞} three times the 'zero-time' conductance, i. e. the conductance expected for the release of both the bound chloride ions (see text).

It has been found that the rate of release of chloride ion is independent of any of the reagents studied ; the rate in presence of any of these reagents is the same as in the pure aqueous solution of the complex. The reaction in pure aqueous solution takes place without any significant change in pH in the course of first few days. On longer storage, however, the aqueous solution turns green accompanied by a sharp rise in the pH of the solution which indicates the release of ethylenediamine from the complex.

As a result of the release of two chloride ions from $\text{cis-dichlorobis(ethylenediamine)chromium(III)}$ ion in aqueous solution, the product is expected to be the $\text{diaquobis(ethylenediamine)chromium(III)}$ species. However, the spectrum of the solution (see Fig. 1 ; absorption maximum at 410 and 550nm) after sufficient long time, by which time the reaction is expected to be

completed, does not resemble that of $\text{cis-diaquobis(ethylenediamine)chromium(III)}$ ion or its trans-isomer or an equilibrium mixture of the cis- and the trans-isomers or of the corresponding hydroxoquo or dihydroxo species⁶. The spectrum however resembles closely that of the known diol complex ion⁷:

The absorption spectrum of this complex ion recorded on crystal powder (using bromide salt of the complex) has been reported by Penn⁸. The spectrum shows absorption maxima at 390 and 550 nm. Again, the spectrum of the solution in presence of 1,10-phenanthroline after a few days corresponds to that of the tetrakis (phenanthroline)- μ -dioldichromium(III) complex ion,

reported by Inskeep and Benson⁹. The spectrum of the experimental solution of $\text{cis-Cr}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2^+$ in presence of dipyridyl is also very similar (see Fig. 1) and in all probability the final product formed in this case is

Fig. 1. Formation of diol complex in presence and absence of 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridyl (Temp. 25°-30°) Absorption spectra (in aqueous solution) :

- (A) 0.002M $\text{cis-}[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (freshly prepared solution)
- (B) 0.002M $\text{cis-}[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (solution aged for six days)
- (C) 0.002M $\text{cis-}[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} + 0.02\text{M}$ phenanthroline (solution aged for six days)
- (D) 0.002M $\text{cis-}[\text{Cr}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} + 0.02\text{M}$ dipyridyl (solution aged for six days)

